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DEVELOPMENT OF ANTIMONOPOLY POLICY IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

The development of an Antimonopoly Policy is important for the economic development of Georgia, as it helps to foster competition, protect consumer rights, and ensure fair business practices. Here are a few key reasons why the development of an Antimonopoly Policy is significant: promoting competition, protecting consumer rights, ensuring market efficiency, attracting investment and enhancing business environment. In conclusion, the development of an Antimonopoly Policy in Georgia is crucial for promoting competition, protecting consumer rights, ensuring market efficiency, attracting investment, and aligning with international standards. It provides a framework for fair business practices, stimulates economic development, and contributes to a healthy and competitive business environment.

In the process of the research are used general scientific methods (systemic, structural, functional) and private methods (graphic and those of conformity). Official statistical data existing in the country as well as the data and evaluations officially published by international organizations are also used.

Keywords: Competition law, Competition policy, Antitrust, Consumer protection, Economic regulation

Introduction

In Georgia, as well as in most post-socialist countries, the period of transition to a market economy was characterized by great difficulties and resistance. Obviously, the process of modifying the country's economy on the rails of the market economy was not simple and easy to implement, bringing new, unfaced challenges (Anguridze et al., 2015; Papava, Charaia, 2021). Security problems and modern challenges of the Georgian national currency. Tbilisi State University.). However, it is also clear that in all those countries where this process started and did not achieve any significant success, the main reason for this success was the political will of each individual state, one of the most important elements of which is the realization of a consistent anti-monopoly policy, which in turn must be harmonized. with the outside world and should not

contradict the norms and international obligations established by international standards, at the same time considering major global and local events, supporting or destabilizing implementation of new approaches, for instance Covid-19 global pandemic (Charaia et al., 2021) and/or modern financial instruments bringing new reality to the market (Lashkhi et al., 2022).

Georgia, as a market-oriented country, from the very first year of gaining independence, set a goal to promote free trade and competition, providing equal opportunities for the business and professional (Kvirkaia et al., 2018), to serve the system. The achievement of which would be impossible without the presence of effective levers to identify and prevent the elements hindering the market economy. The latter was achievable precisely under the conditions of

introduction of legal mechanisms of antimonopoly regulation and its practical implementation.

Accordingly, since 1992, the process of formation and formation of antimonopoly policy began in Georgia, which throughout this 30-year history was not always consistent, and in some cases it fell out of the general principles of antimonopoly regulation.

Methodology

The antimonopoly policy of Georgia is examined in this article using a mixed-methods approach, which combines several research techniques. The study uses both primary and secondary data sources to present a thorough examination of Georgia's legal system, enforcement procedures, difficulties, and future possibilities for antimonopoly policy:

- Literature Review: The academic literature, policy papers, reports, and case studies pertaining to Georgia's antimonopoly policy were all carefully examined. The objectives of this stage were to lay a theoretical framework, identify significant research gaps, and comprehend the current issues and leading practices in the area of competition regulation.

- Legal Analysis: The Law on Competition and pertinent laws were thoroughly examined. The study looked at the legislation's contents and breadth, as well as the GNCA's authority and duties, merger control laws, and the definition of anticompetitive acts. This investigation shed light on the Georgian legal system's antimonopoly regulatory structure. Qualitative Data Collection: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key stakeholders involved in antitrust regulation in Georgia. These interviews involved officials from the GNCA, representatives from relevant government agencies, legal experts, and industry professionals. The interviews aimed to gain insights into the practical implementation of antimonopoly policy, challenges faced by enforcement agencies, and potential areas for improvement.

- Case Studies: A few noteworthy antitrust investigations and enforcement actions in Georgia were the subject of in-depth case studies. These incidents were found after consulting with specialists and reviewing available public information. The case studies provide thorough illustrations of how antimonopoly policy was used, the difficulties faced, and the results obtained.

- Comparative study: To measure Georgia's antimonopoly policy against best practices in other countries, an international comparative study was conducted. This required researching the antitrust laws of nations with comparable economic situations or regulatory difficulties (Blair & Sokol, 2017). The comparison research helped to identify prospective policy changes and Georgia's improvement plans.

To give a thorough knowledge of Georgia's antimonopoly policy, the results from the qualitative interviews, data analysis, case studies, and comparative analysis were combined. The study findings form the foundation for this article's examination of obstacles and opportunities in the next parts.

Stages of antimonopoly policy in Georgia

The purpose of the present study is to briefly present and evaluate the history of the formation and implementation of the antimonopoly policy in Georgia for more than three decades, which in turn can be divided into the following stages:

First stage: March 1992 - June 1996. This period begins with the adoption of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Georgia dated March 17, 1992 (No. 323) "On some measures of demonopolization of economic activity in the Republic of Georgia". Later, the Decree of the State Council of the Republic of Georgia dated October 16, 1992, "On Limitation of Monopolistic Activities and Development of Competition" was adopted, thus defining the organizational and legal bases for the development of competition, prevention, limitation and prevention of monopolistic activities and unfair competition. In the same period, the Decree of the President of Georgia dated March 1995 (No. 60) "On the protection of consumers from unfair advertising" was adopted, on the basis of which, in parallel with the implementation of the function of supporting entrepreneurship and the development of competition, as well as protecting the rights of consumers and supporting market needs (Abashidze, 2023), the function of controlling advertising activities was assigned to the Ministry of Economy of Georgia (Antimonopoly Main Department of Politics) (Chinchilakashvili, 2017).

It should also be noted here that the first stage of competition policy formation in Georgia coincided with the process of mass privatization, which is why great caution and prudence were needed in the implementation of this policy. Accordingly, if we judge from today's perspective, it is clear that the Competition Authority of Georgia (through the internal structural units of the central apparatus of the Ministry of Economy) more or less successfully coped with the tasks facing it (preventing new monopolistic formations and improving the business environment) during that period (Gakharia, Gelashvili 2014).

Second stage: July 1996 - June 2002. This period coincides with the process of formation of competition law in the country on the constitutional basis. This period is connected with the establishment of a more or less independent antimonopoly body in Georgia - the State Antimonopoly Service of Georgia under the Ministry of Economy of Georgia.

In the same period, Georgian laws "On monopoly activity and competition", "On protection of consumer rights" and "On advertising" were adopted, and dozens of normative acts based on these laws (only 21 sub-normative rules in the direction of consumer rights protection) were adopted.

In the same period, the State Antimonopoly Service of Georgia implemented a number of such activities, which significantly improved the competitive environment in individual commodity markets. The relevant commodity markets were intensively researched in order to assess the competitive environment in these markets and identify economic agents with dominant/monopoly status. In addition, important steps have been taken both in terms

of protection of consumer rights and regulation of advertising activities.

The fact that the activity performed by the State Antimonopoly Service of Georgia during this period was evaluated at a rather high level - in the 1999 report of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, which dealt with issues of competition policy in post-communist countries, is significant and significant.

The third stage: July 2002 - November 2004. This is the period when the mechanisms for the realization of a unified centralized antimonopoly policy begin to be divided (redistributed) in a narrow field, which was created a legal basis by the adoption of the Law of Georgia on "Independent Regulatory Bodies".

Simultaneously with the adoption of the aforementioned law, an amendment was made to the Law of Georgia "On Monopoly Activity and Competition", according to which the regulated sectors of the economy were removed from the area of supervision of the Antimonopoly Service. In addition, according to the amendments made to the Law of Georgia "On Statistics" on December 25, 2002, the State Antimonopoly Service of Georgia became unavailable to the primary data on the entrepreneurial activity of an economic agent (the volume of production of products), which is the basis of its activity (the study of commodity markets and the assessment of the competitive environment in these markets) became an obstacle.

Due to the mentioned and a number of other circumstances, the activity of the State Antimonopoly Service, in terms of competition protection, was carried out with certain delays during this period. Accordingly, the main focus was shifted to the areas of protection of consumer rights and regulation of advertising activities.

Fourth stage: December 2004 - August 2005. "This is the period when, without making any changes to the existing competition law in Georgia, a radical reduction in the number of the country's main competition body took place (01.12.2004), thus effectively rejecting (in the enforcement part, not at the legislative level), the competition policy implemented since 1992 and started intensive Work to establish competition law based on a new vision (the concept of letting the economy do its thing)". Accordingly, the State Antimonopoly Service of Georgia did not start studying new cases during this period (even though it had the right to do so at the legislative level) and in parallel with the work on the competition framework law based on the new vision, its activity was limited to involvement in ongoing (previously started and unfinished) court disputes. This period ends - with the liquidation of the State Antimonopoly Service of Georgia (August 19, 2005).

The fifth stage: September 2005 - June 2010. This period begins after the entry into force of the law of June 3, 2005 - "On Free Trade and Competition" (two months after its publication) and the liquidation of the State Antimonopoly Service of Georgia. A number of norms defined by the new competition framework law were not in line with the advanced international practice in this direction. (Gerber, 2018). It did not

include a significant part of the general provisions of competition and established only the regulations for the granting of consent determined by state aid and targeted state programs (procedures for agreement with the competition agency).

Sixth stage: July 2010 - December 2011. During this period, the state sub-departmental institution of the Ministry of Economic Development of Georgia - Free Trade and Competition Agency was liquidated, and in its place, a public law legal entity of the same name was created under the umbrella of the Government of Georgia. In accordance with the regulation approved by the government, the task of the Free Trade and Competition Agency of the Free Trade Association was defined - to develop a comprehensive strategy of competition policy and submit it to the Government of Georgia. Consequently, the agency's activities were limited to working on this strategy project, which is why it did not actually carry out any other activities during this entire period (Gal, 2017).

On the other hand, the comprehensive strategy of the competition policy prepared by the Free Trade and Competition Agency of the State of Georgia was adopted by the Decree of the Government of Georgia dated December 3, 2010 N1551, after which, in fact, the agency exhausted its powers (Gelashvili, 2016).

Seventh stage: January 2012 - March 2014.

During this period, without making any changes to the Competition Framework Law ("On Free Trade and Competition") (without reflecting the general principles of competition in it), the union (merger) of the State Competition Agency and the State Procurement Agencies of the State Procurement Agency took place mechanically from January 01, 2012.

Later, already on May 8, 2012, a new law was adopted - "On Free Trade and Competition" - which repealed the law of June 3, 2005 with the same name. This new framework competition law already contained the basic principles of competition and its individual provisions were more or less harmonized with the relevant norms of the European Union (Whish, 2015). However, the law as a whole was flawed, due to which it could not ensure full compliance with the principles of healthy competition. Accordingly, practical activities (in terms of assessing the competitive environment on the commodity markets and detecting and preventing anti-competitive actions), due to the lack of an appropriate legislative (sub-legal) base of the State Procurement Agency and the State Competition Agency, were not implemented during the entire seventh stage.

The eighth stage: April 2014 - October 2020. This period begins with the correction of existing gaps in the framework competition law (by making appropriate legislative amendments) and the establishment of an independent legal entity under public law - the Competition Agency of the National Competition Authority (established on April 14, 2014).

In addition, in parallel with the amendments made to the competition law, the competition agency developed and adopted relevant subordinate normative acts (5 orders of the chairman of the agency and 2

government resolutions), after their entry into force (October 1, 2014), the competition agency began intensive work in all areas of competition law enforcement. - In addition to the regulated sectors of the economy, competition legislation does not apply to business.

The ninth stage: November 2020 - March 2022. This period begins with the amendments made to the Law of Georgia "On Competition" (the main part entered into force on November 4, 2020). The package of amendments to the competition framework law was prepared within the framework of the EU-funded project "Support to the Georgian Competition Agency" and it was supposed to eliminate such issues in the law, which are considered problematic, such as - a) imperfection of the enforcement mechanisms provided for by the legislation in the process of studying the violation of the law, b) competition Inefficiency and malfunction of the scope of cooperation between the agency and the regulatory bodies of the regulated sphere of economy, c) Inefficiency of the regulatory norms of concentration, d) Incompleteness of procedural issues and deadlines of administrative proceedings carried out by the state government, the government of the autonomous republic and the local government body, e) In case of confirmation of the fact of unfair competition (Article 113 of the Law) failure to consider the sanction, f) replacement of the single-person management of the agency with collegial management and different mechanisms of law enforcement, terminology, etc. debugging and refinement.

In order to correct the mentioned shortcomings, as a result of the amendments made to the law, it can be said unequivocally that the competition framework law in force in the country, in the main, came into compliance (harmonized) with the advanced international practice, which in turn improved (increased) the quality of the work of the national competition agency of the country.

With the legislative changes adopted during this period, the competition legislation applies to the regulated sectors of the economy and its enforcement is carried out by the regulatory bodies of the relevant field.

In the same period, the first steps were taken in the country in terms of the formation of the anti-dumping policy and its implementation in practice. In particular, in order to protect local industry from dumping imports and/or possible damage - the law adopted in July 2020 - "On the introduction of anti-dumping measures in trade" came into effect on January 1, 2021, and to ensure its enforcement, the Department of Anti-Dumping Measures was established in the National Competition Agency of Georgia.

Also, from January 1, 2021, as part of the central apparatus of the National Competition Agency, the apparatus of the Dispute Review Board, which serves - the independent body created on the basis of the amendments made to the Law of Georgia "On State Procurement" in July 2020 - the State Procurement Dispute Review Board. On the other hand, 1) the council is an impartial and independent body created on

the basis of this law, whose goal is to resolve disputes quickly, effectively and fairly in accordance with the same law, 2) the council is separate from all bodies/persons, is independent in its activities and obeys only the law, 3) The regulation of the Council is approved by the resolution of the Government of Georgia, 4) The Chairman of the Council submits to the Parliament of Georgia, the Prime Minister of Georgia and the Agency no later than March 1 of each year, information on the activities of the Council for the past year. . . ." (7, Article 232). As we can see, on the one hand, the dispute review board in the field of state procurement is a separate, independent body, and on the other hand, the department that serves this board is a constituent part of the structure of the National Competition Agency of Georgia.

The tenth stage: the period from April 2022 to the present. This period begins - with the adoption of the Law of Georgia "On Protection of Consumer Rights" adopted by the Parliament of Georgia in 2022 (29.03.2022), which entered into force on April 1, 2022. Accordingly, in the territory of Georgia, in order to identify the facts of the prevention of violation of consumer rights and to promote the restoration of violated rights, and to respond appropriately, the National Competition Agency of Georgia started receiving and reviewing applications from November 1, 2022, which was preceded by the establishment of the consumer rights protection department in the central office of the agency and its corresponding Staffing.

As for the regulated sectors of the economy, the enforcement of the consumer rights protection policy, like the competition policy, is carried out by the regulatory bodies of the sector.

In the same period, the "TWINNING" project "Strengthening the capabilities of the Georgian Competition Agency" funded by the European Union was launched and is currently ongoing, within the framework of which, a team of professionals from the competition agencies of Lithuania and Austria provides consultations and technical support.

The purpose of this project is to strengthen the direction of competition and consumer protection policy within the framework of the association agreement, to improve the legal status of consumers in Georgia, to ensure a high level of protection, to strengthen the culture of behavior based on respect. Also, in accordance with EU best practices, strengthening the institutional and human resources capacity of GNCA.

Thus, since the end of March of last year, the process of performing the functions of protection of consumer rights, along with the important functions of antimonopoly regulation and anti-dumping measures, has become the most important part of the activity of the National Competition Agency.

The eleventh stage: the period after the establishment of the Competition Council. In our opinion, after the National Competition Agency of Georgia becomes a collegial management body, a new eleventh stage of competition policy enforcement will take place. The new edition of Article 171 of the Law

of Georgia "On Competition", which provides for the transition to a collegial model of agency management, entered into force on June 1, 2021. However, as a result of legislative changes implemented on December 22, 2022, this deadline was extended to January 1, 2025. Accordingly, from the moment of entry into force of this change, the manager/leader of the agency will not be the chairman (as it is today), but a five-member council elected by the parliament (through a public competition) for a five-year term. Also, from this period, the position of the executive director, who is appointed and dismissed by the Prime Minister of Georgia for a period of five years, according to the rule of open competition (Gakharia, Kenjebekishvili 2018). On the other hand, the transition to a collegial form of management of the National Competition Authority will further bring the competition policy implemented in the country closer to the European, advanced practice.

Twelfth stage: Enforcement of unified antimonopoly policy through the Competition Agency/Council in all sectors of the economy, including infrastructure sectors/regulated sectors. As we mentioned above (ninth period), after the amendments made to the Law of Georgia "On Competition" in 2020, it applies to all sectors, including the regulated sectors of the economy. However, its enforcement - in the regulated areas is carried out not through the National Competition Agency, centrally, but directly by the regulatory bodies/commissions of the field. Thus, after the changes of September 16, 2020, a complaint/statement regarding a possible violation of competition in the regulated sphere of the economy or a notification regarding concentration will be submitted to the regulatory bodies of the regulated sphere of the economy - a) National Bank of Georgia; b) Energy and Water Supply Regulatory Commission of Georgia and c) National Communications Commission of Georgia.

Conclusions and recommendations

Obviously, the fact that the law of Georgia "on competition" applies to all areas of the economy is a step forward in the enforcement of competition law. However, the existing model of its enforcement in Georgia (3 independent regulatory bodies together with the National Competition Agency) does not represent advanced international, including European, practice. Therefore, after the country abandons the narrow sectoral practice of competition law enforcement and starts enforcing this policy in all sectors of the economy, directly through the National Competition Agency of Georgia - this will be the very beginning of a new stage that will be fully harmonized with advanced international and primarily European practice.

Based on all of the above, taking into account that the level of compliance of antimonopoly regulation and its executive institution with international standards is a determinant of the quality of market relations in the country, it can be said that the activities carried out in Georgia in terms of the implementation of competition legislation (starting from 1992), as a whole, depending

on the actual circumstances - in some cases was successful and in some cases unsuccessful.

Thus, if we evaluate the effectiveness of the antimonopoly/competition policy implemented in Georgia by years, we will see that it is most prominent in the initial and last periods. That is, from the first, second and eighth stages onwards - the practice of antimonopoly regulation can really be considered successful or at least partially successful.

Also, it can be safely said that after the institutional change planned from January 1, 2025, and finally, with the introduction of the implementation process of the unified antimonopoly policy in the country through one body (the National Competition Agency/Competition Council), the process of practical implementation of the antimonopoly policy in the country will be even more successful. What will make the business environment in Georgia even more secure and attractive.

Based on the research done we would like to provide several recommendations which could promote the antimonopoly activities farther in Georgia:

- Strengthen institutional independence by providing the Georgian National Competition Agency (GNCA) with sufficient funding, fiscal assistance, and legislative safeguards against political meddling (Kovzanadze, 2016). This will improve the agency's capacity to fairly and effectively enforce antitrust laws.

- Increase the GNCA's capacity for enforcement by providing it with more staff, technical equipment, and training programs. This will improve the GNCA's capacity for both enforcement and investigation. This will make it possible for the agency to handle more cases, carry out thorough market assessments, and successfully oppose anticompetitive behavior.

- Encourage the GNCA to proactively identify possible antitrust breaches and initiate investigations rather of depending primarily on complaints and reports in order to promote proactive investigations. This proactive strategy can aid in early detection and correction of anticompetitive activity, promoting a competitive market environment.

- Simplify Merger Control: Examine and update the merger control rules to make sure they properly identify mergers and acquisitions that could be anticompetitive. To prevent the establishment or strengthening of dominating market positions, mergers that have the potential to significantly reduce competition should be given more examination, especially in industries that are already highly concentrated. Boost Collaboration: Encourage methods for communication and collaboration between the GNCA and other pertinent government organizations, such as sector-specific regulators and consumer protection agencies. Through collaboration, anticompetitive activities in many economic sectors may be found and addressed.

- Implement public awareness campaigns to inform customers, companies, and the broader public about the value of competition and the negative repercussions of anticompetitive activity. Encourage a culture of competition that supports adherence to antitrust laws and creates a level playing field for all market players.

- International Cooperation: Look into possibilities for knowledge-sharing and international cooperation with antitrust authorities from other nations. Engage in bilateral or multilateral agreements to share best practices, knowledge, and experience in the area of competition regulation so that Georgia can gain insight from antitrust systems that have shown to be effective.

- Periodic Legislative Review: The Law on Competition and its regulations should be regularly reviewed to maintain their efficacy and applicability in tackling new antitrust issues (Fox, Crane, 2018). Keep up with global trends and change the legal system to reflect shifting market dynamics and technology improvements.

- Research and Data Collection: Encourage research and data gathering on matters relating to competition, such as market studies, sector-specific analysis, and evaluations of the economic effects of antitrust laws. The evidence-based ideas from this study can help Georgia's antimonopoly laws be continually improved.

- Collaboration with Civil Society: Encourage collaboration with academic institutions, professional groups, and civil society organizations to take use of their knowledge and advance public involvement in the creation and assessment of antimonopoly regulations. This involvement may help make the decision-making process more open and inclusive.

With the help of these suggestions, Georgia's antimonopoly policy will be able to better address its problems and create an atmosphere that encourages efficient markets and fair competition. By putting these recommendations into practice, the antitrust system can be made more effective and Georgia's economy can flourish sustainably.

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